

1 **TITLE PAGE**

2 **Title:** Repeated low-intensity prescribed fires decrease stocks and change attributes of coarse
3 woody debris

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12 **Running title:** Effects of prescribed fire on coarse woody debris

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14

15 *Abstract.* Previous studies have found negligible effects of single prescribed fires on coarse
16 woody debris (CWD) but the cumulative effects of repeated low-intensity prescribed fires are
17 unknown. This represents a knowledge gap for environmental management since repeated
18 prescribed fires are a key management response to increasing wildfire hazards, and since CWD is
19 recognized as critical to forest biodiversity and functioning. We examined the effects of repeated
20 low-intensity prescribed fires on the attributes and stocks of (fallen) CWD in a mixed-species
21 eucalypt forest of temperate Australia. Prescribed fire treatments were a factorial combination of
22 two seasons (Autumn, Spring) and two frequencies (3-yearly 'Low', 10 yearly 'High'), were
23 replicated over five study areas, and involved 2 to 7 low-intensity fires over 27 years. Charring due
24 to prescribed fires variously changed carbon and nitrogen concentrations and C to N ratios of
25 CWD pieces depending on decay class, but did not affect mean wood density. CWD biomass and
26 C and N stocks were significantly less in Fire than Control treatments. Decreases in total C stocks
27 of c. 8 Mg ha⁻¹ in Fire treatments were not balanced by minor increases in pyrogenic (char) C (c.
28 0.3 Mg ha⁻¹). Effects of prescribed fire type included significantly less C and N stocks in rotten
29 CWD in High than Low frequency treatments, and in the largest CWD in Autumn than Spring
30 treatments. Our study demonstrates that repeated low-intensity prescribed fires have the potential
31 to significantly decrease CWD stocks, in pieces of all sizes and particularly decayed pieces, and to
32 change CWD chemical attributes. CWD is at best a minor stock of pyrogenic C under such fire
33 regimes. These findings suggest a potential management trade-off between sustained reduction of
34 wildfire risk, and the consequences of decreased CWD C stocks, and of changes in CWD as a
35 habitat and biogeochemical substrate. Nonetheless, negative impacts on CWD of repeated low-
36 intensity prescribed fires could be lessened by fire intervals of 10 rather than 3 years (to decrease
37 losses of decayed CWD), and fires in moist rather than dry conditions (to conserve large CWD).

38 *Key words:* carbon, C; char; coarse woody debris quality; eucalypt forest; fire regime; nitrogen,
39 N; prescribed fire frequency; prescribed fire season; pyrogenic carbon; southeastern Australia;
40 wood decay; wood density.

41

42 INTRODUCTION

43 Prescribed fire, the deliberate application of fire to forest fuels to achieve specific goals, is
44 a worldwide management practice (Fernandes et al. 2003). While used as an ecosystem
45 management tool for regeneration, habitat management, and weed and pathogen control (e.g.
46 Carter and Darwin Foster 2004, Firn et al. 2008), a key goal in fire-prone regions is to reduce
47 wildfire risk by decreasing fuel hazards (Youngblood et al. 2008, Vaillant et al. 2009, McCaw
48 2013). Depending on conditions, fuel hazards might be reduced after a single prescribed fire for 3
49 – 15 years (Fernandes et al. 2003, Agee and Skinner 2005, Stephens et al. 2012), so that repeated
50 prescribed fires at regular intervals are often required to maintain hazard reduction objectives
51 (Fernandes et al. 2003, Battaglia et al. 2008). While many studies have examined effects of single
52 prescribed fires (Boerner et al. 2008, Loucks et al. 2008, van Mantgem et al. 2011), very few have
53 analyzed the longer-term impact of repeated fires on fuel reduction and on ecosystem functioning
54 (but see: Sorensen et al. 2011, Lewis and Debuse 2012, Bennett et al. in press). This represents a
55 significant knowledge gap in the environmental management of temperate forests where
56 prescribed fires are seen as vital to mitigating the negative impacts of ‘mega-fires’, which are
57 predicted to increase in frequency under climate change (Adams 2013).

58 Coarse woody debris (CWD), defined here as fallen dead woody material in all stages of
59 decay, is important to fire impacts (Hollis et al. 2011), but is also a key structural component of
60 many forest ecosystems (Harmon et al. 1986). CWD provides essential habitat for small
61 vertebrates (Ecke et al. 2002, Andruskiw et al. 2008), and for insects, fungi, microorganisms and
62 non-vascular plants, whose community composition vary with wood size and decay (Grove 2002,
63 Bässler et al. 2010, Browning et al. 2010). As large rotten logs, CWD provides heterogeneous
64 microsites that promote the germination and establishment of a diversity of tree species (Christie

65 and Armesto 2003, Marx and Walters 2008, Bailey et al. 2012). In addition, CWD has a key role
66 in biogeochemical processes, including as a long-term source of nutrients (Fisk et al. 2002,
67 Romero et al. 2005, Marañón-Jiménez and Castro 2013), particularly nitrogen (Hart 1999), and as
68 a mediating influence on soil structure (Jia-bing et al. 2005). Despite recognition of CWD as an
69 indicator of both forest biodiversity and functioning (Bunnell and Houde 2010, Rondeux and
70 Sanchez 2010), the influence of common management practices like prescribed fire on CWD
71 attributes remain under-examined (Hyde et al. 2011), particularly in the context of temperate
72 Australia (Hollis et al. 2011).

73 Limited available evidence suggests prescribed fires have the potential to influence both
74 the quantity ('stocks') and the attributes of CWD. Reported changes in CWD stocks due to single
75 prescribed fires vary from decreases (Knapp et al. 2005) to no detectable effects (Kolaks et al.
76 2004, Graham and McCarthy 2006, Loucks et al. 2008). In addition, there is consistent evidence to
77 suggest that prescribed fires will influence the distribution of CWD stocks by decay class due to
78 greater consumption of dead rotten wood (80 – 90%) than of sound wood (30 – 45%; Stephens and
79 Moghaddas 2005, Youngblood et al. 2008, Uzoh and Skinner 2009). Chemical attributes of CWD
80 might also be changed by fire through losses of nitrogen due to volatilization, and through
81 increases in concentrations of carbon with charring (Boerner 1982, Donato et al. 2009). In turn,
82 such fire-induced changes in CWD physicochemical attributes have the potential to significantly
83 alter biogeochemical cycling (Harmon et al. 1986, Wang et al. 2002, Mackensen and Bauhus
84 2003).

85 The nature of prescribed fire effects on CWD will depend on fire and fuel conditions. Fires
86 have the capacity to both produce (through tree death and fall) and to consume CWD; so post-fire
87 CWD stocks represent the balance of these two processes (Polo et al. 2013). For example, both
88 tree mortality (North and Hurteau 2011, van Mantgem et al. 2013) and CWD consumption (Hollis

89 2011) are known to increase with fire intensity and/or severity. It follows that CWD consumption
90 has been found to be greater after prescribed fires in autumn, when fuels were dry (and fire
91 intensity greater), than in spring, when fuels were moist (Knapp et al. 2005, Stephens and
92 Moghaddas 2005). On the other hand, the degree of CWD charring is expected to be greater when
93 fuels are moist since moisture promotes low intensity combustion (Pyne et al. 1996, Donato et al.
94 2009). Here, it is worth noting that most research on the effects of prescribed fire conditions on
95 CWD has been based on single fires (Kolaks et al. 2004, Graham and McCarthy 2006, Loucks et
96 al. 2008, Uzoh and Skinner 2009), and, thus, the longer-term effects of repeated low-intensity
97 prescribed fires remain unclear (Polo et al. 2013).

98 Effects of prescribed fire on CWD stocks is relevant to current analyses of the carbon costs
99 of prescribed fire regimes, particularly relative to wildfires (Campbell et al. 2011, North and
100 Hurteau 2011, Bradstock et al. 2012). Depending on the balance between inputs and outputs,
101 CWD can represent a significant carbon stock – about 18% of total ecosystem carbon in temperate
102 forests (Pregitzer and Euskirchen 2004) – that should be accounted for in forest management
103 practices (Burrascano et al. 2013). As above, prescribed fire effects on CWD stocks will be
104 context-dependent; however, fires also produce char (a form of ‘pyrogenic carbon’; Preston and
105 Schmidt 2006), which, due to its low decomposability, can contribute to long-term carbon stocks
106 (Preston and Schmidt 2006, Donato et al. 2009). Until recently (Donato et al. 2009), the
107 significance of charred CWD as a stock of ‘stable’ pyrogenic carbon has been largely ignored
108 (Adams and Attiwill 2011). Current evidence indicates that conversion of woody biomass to char
109 by fire can be ‘substantial’ (Donato et al. 2009) depending on fire intensity (Preston and Schmidt
110 2006), but that charred material can be consumed in subsequent fires (Preston and Schmidt 2006).
111 However, so far the cumulative effects of repeated low-intensity fires on CWD pyrogenic C have
112 not been evaluated.

113 Our study examines the effects of repeated low-intensity prescribed fires on CWD stocks
114 and attributes in a fire-tolerant eucalypt forest of south-eastern Australia. In one of Australia's
115 most detailed and long-term prescribed fire experiments (Adams and Attiwill 2011), we examine
116 the effects of four prescribed fire treatments (as a factorial combination of two fire seasons and
117 two fire frequencies) after 27 years, and encompassing 2 – 7 repeated fires. Our objectives were:
118 1) to document the effects of low-intensity prescribed fire on the chemical and structural attributes
119 of CWD; 2) to examine the effects of long-term prescribed fire treatments on CWD stocks
120 (biomass, carbon, nitrogen) by decay and size classes; and 3) to quantify stocks of pyrogenic
121 carbon in CWD after repeated low-intensity prescribed fires. As such, we aim to improve the
122 empirical knowledge base for more complete assessments of the ecological implications of fire
123 regimes involving repeated prescribed fires.

124 MATERIALS AND METHODS

125 *Field areas and experimental design*

126 The study included five areas within a 25 km radius in the Wombat State Forest, which
127 straddles the Great Divide about 100km north-west of Melbourne, Victoria, south-eastern
128 Australia (37°27'S, 144°17'E). The study areas sit upon Kandosols ('stony earths') and Dermosols
129 ('friable earths, motted duplex soils') (ASRIS 2011) derived from Ordovician sedimentary rocks
130 (Rowan et al. 2000). The climate is temperate, with mean monthly minimum temperatures ranging
131 from 2°C to 12°C, and mean monthly maximums ranging from 7°C to 24°C. Frosts are common,
132 particularly in winter (mean of 55 per year; Tolhurst and Flinn 1992). Mean annual rainfall is in
133 the range 800 – 900 mm, with about 70% falling in winter and spring (Bennett et al. in press).

134 The native vegetation is predominantly open forest (Specht 1981) with tree heights 10 to
135 40 m, projective foliage cover 30 to 70%, and under-bark basal area 30 to 40 m² ha⁻¹ (Bennett et
136 al. in press). Forests of this type are predicted to contain the majority of Victoria's forest carbon
137 stores due to their moderate productivity and extensive distribution (Kaye 2009). The forest is
138 dominated by three coexisting eucalypt species: *Eucalyptus obliqua* L'Hér. ('Messmate'), *E.*
139 *radiata* Sieber ex DC. ('Narrow-leaved peppermint'), and *E. rubida* H. Deane and Maiden
140 ('Candlebark'). The understorey is characterised by a sparse shrub layer to 2–4 m height (e.g.
141 *Acacia* spp.), and a ground layer dominated by Austral bracken (*Pteridium esculentum* (G.Forst.)
142 Cockayne), native perennial grasses (e.g. *Tetrarrhena juncea* R. Br., *Poa sieberiana* Vickery),
143 forbs (e.g. *Gonocarpus tetragynus* Labill., *Viola hederacea* Labill.), and rushes (*Lomandra* spp.;
144 Tolhurst 2003).

145 A long-term prescribed fire experiment has been maintained in the Wombat State Forest
146 since 1985. Previously the area had been periodically thinned to remove trees of low commercial
147 value from the 1930s to 1960s/70s. Details on the experimental design are provided in Bennett et
148 al. (in press) and Tolhurst et al. (2003). Briefly, the experiment conforms to a 2x2 factorial plus
149 control in a randomized block design, involving five study areas (blocks) locally known as the
150 'Fire Effects Study Areas' (FESA) ranging from 19 ha to 128 ha. Five treatments, randomly
151 allocated to treatment areas of 3 – 35 ha, were: a long un-burnt control plus a factorial combination
152 of two fire seasons, Autumn ('A') and Spring ('S'), and two fire frequencies, High frequency ('H',
153 nominally every 3 years) and Low frequency ('L', nominally every 10 years). Control treatments
154 were last burnt by wildfire between 1931 and 1974, and prescribed fires in all treatments were
155 considered low-intensity (Tolhurst and Flinn 1992). Numbers of prescribed fires since 1985 were
156 greater in High (6) than Low frequency treatments (3), and the last prescribed fires were more
157 recent to the time of measurement (4 versus 7 years; Table 1). Mean scorch heights were

158 significantly lower in High (4.8 m) than Low frequency treatments (7.0 m), although there were no
159 significant differences in mean flame height among treatments (average of 0.4 m). The Forest Fire
160 Danger Index (FFDI) and Soil Dryness Index (SDI) indicated significantly drier conditions for
161 Autumn than Spring fires, although mean rates of spread were significantly higher in Spring (1.35
162 m min⁻¹) than Autumn fires (0.56 m min⁻¹; Table 1).

163 **Insert Table 1 here**

164 *CWD measurements in treatment areas*

165 Two types of plots were used for coarse woody debris (CWD) measurements. The first,
166 assessed August to November 2011, consisted of three circular plots (18 m radius, c. 0.1ha) per
167 treatment area, which were also assessed for other key carbon stocks (Bennett et al. in press). The
168 second, established in 1985 prior to the establishment of prescribed fire treatments, was a single
169 rectangular plot (30 x 35 m) per treatment area consisting of 18, 10-m transects systematically
170 arranged in 6 rows of 3, with 5 m between adjacent rows. These 18 transects were regularly
171 assessed to 1999, and in early 2012 as part of the broader FESA experiment. Only the 2012
172 measures were included here because measurement protocols were the same as those used in the
173 circular plots.

174 CWD was assessed using the line-intercept method along two perpendicular transects (each
175 36 m) running north-to-south and east-to-west through the circular plot centre point, and along the
176 18 transects of the rectangular plot (Van Wagner 1968). This gave a total transect length per
177 treatment area of 396 m, well above the minimum 100 m recommended for accurate quantification
178 of CWD volumes in comparable eucalypt forests (Woldendorp et al. 2004).

179 CWD was defined as all fallen dead woody material (branches, boles, logs, large charcoal
180 pieces) that was not rooted in the soil, and with a minimum cross-sectional diameter > 25 mm
181 (McKenzie et al. 2000). Each CWD piece whose central axis intersected a transect was assessed at
182 the point of intersection for: remaining cross-sectional area (RCSA, assuming the piece was
183 originally circular, to the nearest 5%); diameter (mm) perpendicular to the central axis (of the
184 assumed full circle); source ('natural' or 'sawn'); char class; and decay class. A char class was
185 assigned based on the presence or absence of charring at any point on the circumference at the
186 point of intersection as follows: 'Non-charred', 'Superficially charred' (char depth ≤ 0.5 mm), or
187 'Deeply charred' (char depth > 0.5 mm). Decay was classified using a five-point system based on
188 previous assessments of eucalypt CWD (Grove et al. 2009, Hollis et al. 2011), as follows: D1, no
189 decay, supported weight, retained original shape, bark intact/mostly attached, twigs potentially
190 present, fissures and cracks absent; D2, weakly decayed, hard when kicked, retained shape, bark
191 and twigs absent, signs of discolouration, small cracks/fissures (1-2 cm deep) possible; D3,
192 moderately decayed, potentially soft when kicked but retained shape, bark absent, sapwood
193 slightly soft, cracks/ fissures possible (3-4 cm deep), moss/fungi possible; D4, very decayed, soft
194 to kick with some loss of shape, did not support weight, sapwood decayed and likely missing in
195 parts, original colour faded, moss/fungi/invading roots likely; D5, substantially decayed, without
196 form, wood soft or largely disintegrated, bark and sapwood largely absent, heartwood rotten,
197 moss/fungi/invading roots likely.

198 *CWD characterization*

199 In addition to the line-intercept assessment of CWD loads, CWD pieces were sampled
200 (from beyond the measurement plots) for detailed characterization of char depth, wood density,
201 and carbon (C) and nitrogen (N) concentrations. At each study area, two replicate pieces were

202 sampled from every available combination of two char classes (Non-charred, Deeply charred), two
203 diameter size classes ('Small' ≤ 225 mm, 'Large' > 225 mm; based on woody fuel size classes of
204 Hollis et al. 2010), and five decay classes (D1 to D5). As indicated by the line-intercept data, not
205 all combinations were present at each study area, leading to a final sample of 165 complete pieces.
206 Samples, as a complete cross-section of a 5 cm wide disk, were immediately sealed in a ziplock
207 plastic bag, and were maintained at constant humidity at 4°C until further processing. All were
208 eucalypt samples, but no attempt was made to identify species since this was not discernible for
209 highly charred or decayed pieces.

210 In the laboratory, char depth (mm) of each Deeply charred CWD sample was measured as
211 the mean depth at four equidistant points around the cross sectional profile. As relevant according
212 to the state of decay, Large pieces (> 225 mm) were divided into concentric rings of different wood
213 types based on their softness (Chao et al. 2008). The 'Hard' wood type formed the outer ring of the
214 disc and could not be broken by hand; the 'Soft' wood type formed an inner ring and could be torn
215 apart from the Hard wood by hand; and the 'Crumbly' wood type was highly decomposed at the
216 core of the disc. Small pieces (≤ 225 mm) in decay classes 1, 2, and 3 were generally composed of
217 one wood type ('Hard' to 'Soft'), and were thus treated as a single 'Combined' wood type. As
218 relevant, Small pieces in decay classes 4 and 5 were classified as Combined or were divided into
219 Hard, Soft and/or Crumbly wood types. For all pieces containing more than one wood type, depth
220 of the Hard wood type was recorded and used to calculate its proportional contribution to each
221 piece's full circular cross sectional area, assuming the piece had no voids (CSA, see below).
222 Classification of CWD pieces resulted in 26 wood types, and a total of 323 wood-type samples to
223 be analysed for wood density (Table A1, Appendix).

224 Wood densities were determined using > 100 cm³ intact sub-samples of Hard and Soft
225 wood types, and > 15 cm³ sub-samples of the Crumbly wood type as material wrapped in 1 mm

226 nylon bags of known weight and volume. Sub-samples were submerged in water for 30 min to
227 ensure saturation, and then fresh volume estimated gravimetrically by water displacement (Grove
228 et al. 2009). Sub-samples were then oven-dried at 105°C to constant weight, and wood density (g
229 cm⁻³) was calculated as the dry weight divided by the fresh volume. Wood densities of CWD
230 pieces that contained multiple wood types were calculated as follows:

$$\rho_{piece} = (\rho_{hard} * CSA_{hard}) + \left(\left[\frac{\rho_{soft} + \rho_{crumbly}}{2} \right] * (1 - CSA_{hard}) \right)$$

231 Where ρ is wood density (of the whole piece or of a wood type), and CSA_{hard} is the proportional
232 contribution of the Hard wood type to the piece's cross-sectional area.

233 Of the 323 wood-type samples, 194 were chosen for analysis of C and N concentrations to
234 provide replicates (mode = 6) of each available combination of wood type, size, decay and char
235 class. These were finely ground (< 0.5 mm), and measured for total C and N concentrations by dry
236 combustion using a LECO TruMac-CN (LECO Corporation, Michigan, USA). Mean
237 concentrations by decay/char/wood type combinations were used to calculate C concentrations of
238 CWD pieces that contained multiple wood types, as follows:

$$C\%_{piece} = (C\%_{hard} * CSA_{hard}) + \left(\left[\frac{C\%_{soft} + C\%_{crumbly}}{2} \right] * (1 - CSA_{hard}) \right)$$

239 Where C% is the carbon concentration (of the whole piece or of a wood type), and CSA_{hard} is the
240 proportional contribution of the Hard wood type to the piece's full circular cross-sectional area.

241 *Estimation of CWD Stocks*

242 CWD stocks were calculated on a piece-by-piece basis and then summed by transects
243 within each plot to give four plot values per treatment area. Piece-level estimations first involved
244 calculating a circular cross-sectional area from the measured diameter. This was then adjusted to

245 the remaining cross-sectional area and converted to piece volume using a re-configuration of Van
246 Wagner's (1968) formula:

$$V_i = (4 \pi * (A * RCSA/100)/8L) * 1000$$

247 where V_i is the volume per unit area of piece 'i' ($\text{m}^3 \text{ha}^{-1}$), A is the piece's full cross-sectional area
248 (m^2), $RCSA$ is the remaining cross-sectional area (%), and L (m) is the transect length corrected
249 for slope. For deeply charred pieces (i.e. ignoring negligible effects of superficial charring), this
250 involved calculating the volume of both a non-burnt core and a charred outer rind (after Donato et
251 al. 2009). That is, cross-sectional area of the non-burnt core was calculated using a diameter
252 adjusted for char depth, which was assigned using the mean depth for that size and decay class
253 (from the above-mentioned CWD characterization). Cross-sectional area of the charred rind was
254 then calculated as the difference between the full and non-burnt core cross-sectional areas.

255 Piece volumes ($\text{m}^3 \text{ha}^{-1}$) were converted to biomass (Mg ha^{-1}) using the mean wood density
256 (Mg m^{-3}) for that decay class (as determined from the CWD characterization). Biomass of the
257 charred rind was also multiplied by 0.4 to adjust for mass loss associated with charring (Donato et
258 al. 2009). Carbon stocks (Mg ha^{-1}) were calculated from biomass values using the C concentration
259 for that decay/char class (range of 43% – 50%; as determined from the CWD characterization) for
260 non-burnt pieces/cores, and a C concentration of 70% for charred rinds (Donato et al. 2009). As
261 relevant, values for non-burnt cores and charred rinds were then summed to give total piece C
262 stock. Nitrogen stocks (kg ha^{-1}) were calculated from biomass values using the N concentration for
263 that decay/char class (range of 0.09 % – 4.1%; as determined from the CWD characterization) for
264 non-burnt pieces/cores and charred rinds.

265 *Data analysis*

266 Differences in CWD attributes and effects of prescribed fire treatments on CWD stocks
267 were tested using the Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) models of R (version 2.10.1; R
268 Development Core Team 2009). A factorial plus added control model with area as a random
269 factor, treatment as a fixed factor, and plot nested within treatment by area, was used to examine
270 the overall effects of prescribed fire (Control versus Fire treatments), as well as the effects of
271 prescribed fire season (Autumn versus Spring) and frequency (High versus Low), and their
272 interactions. All variables conformed to assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity, and thus
273 were not transformed.

274 RESULTS

275 *Influence of wood type, charring and decay class on CWD attributes*

276 C and N concentrations and wood density were significantly different among CWD wood
277 types. Differences were most pronounced for the Crumbly wood type, which had significantly
278 lower C concentrations (41.4% versus 48.5%) and significantly higher N concentrations (0.54%
279 versus 0.17%) than all other wood types, leading to nearly 4-fold lower C to N ratios (84 versus
280 311). Wood density significantly decreased from Combined/Hard (mean of 464 kg m⁻³) to Soft
281 (352 kg m⁻³) or Crumbly (315 kg m⁻³) wood types in line with a visible breakdown in wood
282 structure (Fig. 1).

283 Deep charring of outer surfaces significantly increased the mean C concentrations of the
284 Combined, Hard and Soft wood types by about 1.5% (49.3% versus 47.8%; Fig. 1). However, the
285 same charring had no significant effect on the mean N concentration, C to N ratio, or wood density
286 of any of the wood types (Fig. 1).

287 Proportional representation of each wood type in CWD pieces varied with decay class. For
288 example, proportional cross-sectional area of the Hard wood type in Large pieces (>225 mm)
289 decreased from a mean of 70% in D1 ('no decay') and 60% in D2, to 40% in D4 and 20% in D5
290 ('substantially decayed'). In contrast, the percentage number of sampled Large CWD pieces that
291 contained the Crumbly wood type increased from 40% in D3 ('moderately decayed') to 80% in D4
292 and 100% in D5.

293 Differences in wood type composition underpinned significant variation between decay
294 classes in mean C and N concentrations, C to N ratios, and wood densities of whole CWD pieces
295 (Fig. 2). That is, decreases in the proportion of the Hard wood type (and increases in Soft/Crumbly
296 wood types) from D1 to D5 decay classes were associated with increases in whole-piece N
297 concentrations, and with decreases in C to N ratios and wood densities (Fig. 2). Mean C
298 concentrations also tended to decrease from D1 to D5. However, deep charring altered this pattern
299 by significantly increasing C concentrations of pieces in weakly to moderately decayed classes
300 (D2 to D4; Fig. 2). This increase in mean C concentration of whole pieces from D1 to D4 was
301 associated with an increase in mean char depth of Deeply charred pieces from 5 mm (D1) to 36
302 mm (D2), 41 mm (D3) and 70 mm (D4; data not shown). However, charring did not obviously
303 increase the C concentration of D5 pieces, which instead reflected the greater proportions in this
304 decay class of the Crumbly wood type (of lesser C concentrations; Fig. 1). Charring variously
305 changed mean whole-piece N concentrations from a significant increase in decay class D2, to
306 significant decreases in decay classes D3 to D5, contributing to changes in the relative C to N ratio
307 of deeply charred versus non-charred pieces by decay class (Fig. 2).

308 **Insert Figures 1 and 2 here**

309 *CWD piece distribution by size, decay, and char class*

310 On average across all treatment plots, there were 55 CWD pieces per 100 m of transect
311 (plot range 22 – 155). This corresponded to a mean plot CWD volume of 68 m³ ha⁻¹ (range 9 – 407
312 m³ ha⁻¹), with a mean of 96 m³ ha⁻¹ in the long un-burnt Control plots. Most pieces were of
313 ‘natural’ rather than ‘sawn’ origin, with mean proportional counts of ‘sawn’ pieces not
314 significantly different between Control and Fire treatments (12 versus 10 %; data not shown).

315 Proportional counts of CWD pieces decreased with size. That is, on average, 71% of CWD
316 pieces were in the smallest size class (25 – ≤75 mm diameter), while just 6% were > 225 mm in
317 diameter (Fig. 3). Most pieces were in the ‘moderately decayed’ class (D3, 48%), followed by the
318 ‘weakly decayed’ (D2, 32%) and ‘very decayed’ classes (D4, 12%), with relatively few in the ‘no
319 decay’ (D1, 6%) and ‘substantially decayed’ classes (D5, 2%; Fig. 3). Proportionally more Large
320 (> 225 mm) than Small pieces (≤225 mm) were in the ‘rotten’ (D4, D5) decay classes (28% versus
321 14% respectively); nonetheless, of all pieces in the rotten decay classes, only 11% were Large.

322 As expected, and allowing for historical fires prior to this experiment, very few CWD
323 pieces in Control treatments were Superficially or Deeply charred (means of 6% and 1%
324 respectively; Fig. 3). In contrast, a mean of 39% of CWD pieces in fire treatments were
325 Superficially charred, and 30% were Deeply charred (Fig. 3).

326 **Insert Figure 3 here**

327 *Effects of prescribed fire on CWD stocks*

328 Prescribed fire treatments altered the counts and charring of CWD pieces (Fig. 3) thus
329 affecting CWD biomass, C and N stocks (Fig. 4). Mean counts of CWD pieces were significantly
330 less in Fire (0.52 m⁻¹) than Control treatments (0.67 m⁻¹, $P < 0.01$), a pattern that was consistent
331 across all decay and size classes (although not always significant; Fig. 3). This was associated with

332 significantly less total CWD biomass in Fire ($29.6 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1} \pm 2.2 \text{ SE}$) than Control treatments (45.9
333 $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \pm 9.3$; $P < 0.05$; data not shown). In addition, the type of prescribed fire treatment
334 influenced the distribution of CWD pieces by decay and size class. For example, there were
335 significantly higher numbers of CWD pieces in the most decayed classes (D4, D5) and in the
336 middle size class ($150 - \leq 225 \text{ mm diameter}$) in Low than High frequency fire treatments, and in
337 the largest size class ($>500 \text{ mm diameter}$) in Spring than Autumn fire treatments (Fig. 3). That
338 Low than High Frequency treatments had seemingly less impact on CWD piece counts for some
339 decay and size classes was consistent with less CWD charring, as evidenced by significantly more
340 Non-charred and significantly fewer Deeply charred pieces in the Low than High Frequency
341 treatments (Fig. 3).

342 As indicated by the piece counts, CWD stocks of charred C (i.e. C in the charred rind) were
343 significantly greater in Fire (mean $0.28 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \pm 0.02 \text{ SE}$) than Control treatments (0.02 Mg C
344 $\text{ha}^{-1} \pm 0.01$; $P < 0.001$), and in High ($0.33 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \pm 0.04 \text{ SE}$) than Low frequency treatments
345 ($0.22 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \pm 0.03$; $P < 0.01$). Nonetheless, charred C was a comparatively minor stock
346 compared with C in Non-charred CWD, which was significantly greater in Control ($21.8 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1}$
347 $\pm 4.4 \text{ SE}$) than Fire treatments ($13.8 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \pm 1.0$; $P < 0.001$). Thus, charred C, as a proportion
348 of total CWD carbon, was significantly greater in Fire (2.0%) than Control treatments (0.1%; P
349 < 0.001).

350 Significantly less total CWD C stocks in Fire ($14.1 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \pm 1.1 \text{ SE}$) than Control
351 treatments ($21.9 \text{ Mg C ha}^{-1} \pm 4.4$; $P < 0.05$; Fig. 4) were consistent with recent combustion effects
352 as evidenced by charring. That is, greater incidence of charring in prescribed fire treatments was
353 associated not only with fewer CWD pieces (particularly in the more decayed classes; Fig. 3), but
354 also with marked decreases in the remaining cross-sectional area of Deeply versus Non-charred
355 CWD pieces in the relevant decay classes: 73% versus 92% (D2), 65% versus 77% (D3), 42%

356 versus 51% (D4), and 23% versus 40% (D5; data not shown). Similarly, greater CWD C stocks in
357 decay classes D4 and D5 in Low than High frequency fire treatments (Fig. 4) reflected greater
358 counts in these decay classes combined with a lower incidence of deep charring (i.e. fewer pieces
359 consumed and to a lesser degree; Fig. 3). Nonetheless, overall C stocks were lowest in the Autumn
360 Low Frequency treatment ('AL'), and a significant interaction between fire season and frequency
361 indicated that fire season also influenced CWD carbon stocks in prescribed fire treatments (Fig. 4).
362 This was in part due to significantly fewer large pieces ('S5'; Fig. 3), and, then, significantly lower
363 carbon stocks in large pieces in Autumn than Spring treatments (Fig. 4).

364 Patterns in total CWD N stocks among treatments followed those in total C stocks (Fig. 4).
365 However, decreases between Fire and Control treatments were proportionally greater for N than C,
366 so that mean C to N ratios of total CWD stocks were significantly greater in Fire (366) than
367 Control treatments (331). This was likely due both to the differential effect of charring on C and N
368 concentrations (Fig. 2), and to significant proportional decreases in decayed CWD (D4, D5) in fire
369 treatments (Figs 3 and 4), which had the lowest C to N ratios (Fig. 2). Similarly, the above-
370 mentioned greater incidence of charring in High than Low frequency fire treatments likely
371 contributed to significantly greater C to N ratios in the former (380 versus 351; $P < 0.001$; data not
372 shown).

373 **Insert Figure 4 here**

374 DISCUSSION

375 *Effects of prescribed fire on CWD attributes*

376 As found elsewhere (Grove et al. 2011), the eucalypt-derived CWD in our study was non-
377 homogenous, comprised of a hard outer ring grading to a crumbly inner core. This indicates radial

378 variation in decomposition (Harmon et al. 1986, Grove et al. 2011) consistent with physical
379 fragmentation by invertebrates (Zhou et al. 2007), which facilitates colonization at depth by
380 decomposing fungi and other microorganisms (Grove et al. 2011). Relatively high N
381 concentrations of the Crumbly wood type were consistent with effects of C loss and N
382 immobilization associated with CWD decay (Laiho and Prescott 2004). Decreasing wood densities
383 from Hard to Crumbly wood also conformed to well-established trends that have been used to
384 estimate CWD decomposition rates (Mackensen and Bauhus 2003, Baker et al. 2007, Grove et al.
385 2009). In addition, the distribution of wood types by CWD decay class was consistent with
386 observations of eucalypt CWD elsewhere of more Hard wood types in the ‘sound’ decay classes
387 (D1 to D3), and more Soft and Crumbly wood types in the ‘rotten’ classes (D4, D5; (Grove et al.
388 2011). In turn, whole-piece CWD attributes – increasing N concentration and decreasing density
389 from D1 to D5 – followed trends consistent with changing wood-type composition. This adds
390 weight to previous findings that an assessment system of five externally derived classes
391 successfully captured the main trajectories of internal attribute change in eucalypt CWD (Grove et
392 al. 2011).

393 Consistent with findings from elsewhere (Baldock and Smernik 2002, Czimczik et al.
394 2002), Deep charring significantly increased the C concentration of all but one of our CWD wood
395 types. While charring of the outer ring increased mean C concentrations of the inner Soft wood
396 type, it did not significantly affect C concentrations of the innermost Crumbly wood type. This is
397 consistent with observations of decreasing heat transfer from outer to inner wood (Di Blasi et al.
398 2001), and of cooling effects at the core due to re-condensed water vapor (Janssens 2004),
399 contributing to less potential for thermal alteration of the CWD core than outer wood (Rein 2009).

400 In addition to wood type effects, charring influenced the chemical attributes of whole
401 CWD pieces by decay class. Greater C concentration of charred than non-charred pieces in weak

402 to very decayed classes (D2 to D4) reflected charring effects on the predominant wood types
403 (Hard to Soft). Similarly, no effect of charring on the C concentration of substantially decayed
404 pieces (D5) was consistent with no effect of charring on the Crumbly wood type. In addition, the
405 degree of charring appeared to increase from weakly decayed (D2) to very decayed (D4) pieces, as
406 evidenced by trends of increasing C concentration and mean char depth (36 to 70 mm).
407 Comparative data of CWD char depths by decay classes are lacking, and range from minor
408 variation after wildfires (e.g. 1 to 17 mm; (Donato et al. 2009) to marked effects dependent on
409 burn times in laboratory studies (6 to 40 mm; (Silcock and Shields 2001). The comparatively deep
410 charring of CWD pieces in this study was likely due to the low intensity of our repeated prescribed
411 fires, since char formation is greatest under low-intensity combustion (Pyne et al. 1996). In
412 addition, deeper charring of very decayed than weakly decayed pieces was likely due, in part, to
413 differences in wood attributes and their influence on heat transfer and combustion. For example,
414 the presence of bark in less decayed pieces might have reduced heat transfer due to its lower
415 density (Suleiman et al. 1999), and greater moisture content and lignin to cellulose ratios of more
416 decayed wood might have promoted char formation (Pyne et al. 1996, Cornwell et al. 2009).
417 Additional causes of variable charring depth by decay class remain speculative but would need to
418 consider the cumulative effects of both char production and consumption by multiple fires
419 (Preston and Schmidt 2006). As such, the residence time of CWD pieces might be relevant to char
420 depth, since more decayed pieces would likely have been burnt by more fires (assuming increasing
421 decay represents increasing residence time), but also have been exposed to physical weathering for
422 longer potentially leading to fragmentation and loss of outer char (perhaps explaining our decrease
423 in mean char depth from D4, 70 mm, to D5, 48 mm).

424 Charring further influenced CWD chemical attributes through changes in N concentrations
425 and in C to N ratios of whole pieces that varied by decay class. These significant increases in N

426 concentration (decreases in C to N ratio) with charring of weakly decayed (D2) pieces, but
427 decreases with charring of more decayed (D3 to D5) pieces cannot be readily explained,
428 particularly because we did not detect significant charring effects on N concentrations of
429 individual wood types. Previous studies have found only minor changes in N concentrations of
430 CWD with charring since most N is retained in the char as recalcitrant organic forms (Hansson et
431 al. 2004, Preston and Schmidt 2006). However a fraction of the N can be lost with heating through
432 ammonification and volatilization (Di Blasi 2008), the proportion of which increases with fuel N
433 concentration and decreases with temperature and heating rates (Leppälahti and Koljonen 1995).
434 Thus, since decayed inner wood types (Soft and Crumbly) had higher N concentrations and were
435 likely exposed to lower fire temperatures than outer Hard wood, it seems feasible that burning led
436 to some decreases in N concentrations of Soft and Crumbly wood, which dominated in decay
437 classes D3 to D5. Whatever the underlying mechanisms, our study clearly demonstrates the
438 potential for repeated low-intensity prescribed fires to alter CWD quality, which could have flow-
439 on effects to ecosystem processes like biological decomposition (Baldock and Smernik 2002,
440 Shorohova et al. 2008).

441 *Effects of long-term prescribed fire treatments on CWD stocks*

442 CWD biomass in this study was on average 46 Mg ha⁻¹ in Control plots, which was about
443 11% of the aboveground biomass in live and dead standing trees (406 Mg ha⁻¹; Bennett et al. in
444 press). This mean CWD biomass stock is similar to recent measures in comparable eucalypt
445 forests of south-eastern Australia (Hollis et al. 2011, Volkova and Weston 2013), and close to the
446 Australian mean for open forest (50 Mg ha⁻¹; Woldendorp and Keenan 2005). Nonetheless, our
447 mean CWD volumes in Control plots (96 m³ ha⁻¹) was at the lower end of ranges reported for
448 forests in Europe (10 – 470), North America (10 – 800) and South America (60 – 780 m³ ha⁻¹), and

449 closer to global medians for mature ($68 \text{ m}^3 \text{ ha}^{-1}$) than old-growth moist temperate forests (151 m^3
450 ha^{-1} ; (Burrascano et al. 2013).

451 We found that repeated low-intensity prescribed fires decreased CWD biomass, and that
452 decreases were through both total and partial consumption as evidenced by decreases in piece
453 counts, and decreases in the remaining cross-sectional area of Deeply charred pieces. Mean
454 biomass decreases of 16 Mg ha^{-1} , representing c. 35% of total CWD biomass in Controls, are in
455 contrast to findings from North America of negligible change in CWD biomass after either single
456 (Graham and McCarthy 2006, Loucks et al. 2008, Youngblood et al. 2008) or repeated prescribed
457 fires (Polo et al. 2013). They indicate that consumption of CWD by our repeated low-intensity
458 fires was not counter-balanced by inputs as tree and branch fall. This is consistent with our
459 observations of low overall tree mortality (Bennett et al. in press), and with an absence of other
460 forms of disturbance (e.g. severe storms; Polo et al. 2013) during the 27-year period of our
461 prescribed fire experiment.

462 Our decreases in CWD stocks (biomass, C, N) after repeated prescribed fires were
463 significant for moderately to substantially decayed (D3 to D5) but not the least decayed (D1, D2)
464 CWD. This is consistent with findings from burning experiments of both eucalypt (Tolhurst et al.
465 2006) and non-eucalypt CWD (Youngblood et al. 2008, Hyde et al. 2012). As indicated in the
466 above discussion about charring, differential consumption of CWD by decay class was likely due
467 to a combination of effects including attributes of compositional wood types, and exposure of
468 pieces to both time of weathering and to total number of fires. The importance of physicochemical
469 attributes to relative wood consumption has been demonstrated using laboratory fires, in which
470 consumption was most highly correlated with the increasing lignin content and decreasing density
471 typical of decay (Hyde et al. 2012). In addition, while not estimated here, piece surface area to
472 volume ratios likely influenced CWD consumption since higher ratios provide more area for a

473 smoldering fire to access oxygen (Rein 2009). Surface area to volume ratios typically increase
474 with decay (Wang et al. 2002) as a result of both physical collapse and the micro-fragmentation
475 caused by rotting fungi (Hyde et al. 2012), thereby promoting greater consumption of decayed
476 than sound CWD.

477 We detected significant decreases in CWD stocks across the full range of size classes (25 –
478 75, 150 – 225, >500 mm diameter). Decreases in the smallest size class are consistent with a high
479 probability of fine woody fuel consumption in prescribed fires found elsewhere (Buckley and
480 Corkish 1991, Loucks et al. 2008). However, significant decreases of stocks in larger size classes
481 after repeated low-intensity fires is, to our knowledge, a unique finding, and suggests that
482 consumption of large eucalypt CWD will be a function not only of the intensity of individual fires
483 (Hollis 2011) but also of the cumulative effects of multiple fires. Such decreases in large piece
484 stocks might have been partly due to greater decay (and hence, as above, greater proportional
485 consumption) than in smaller pieces, although only 28% of large pieces (> 225 mm diameter) were
486 classified as rotten (D4 to D5). Despite low numbers relative to small CWD pieces, this decrease
487 in large piece stocks represents a potentially important impact of repeated low-intensity prescribed
488 fires since large pieces (> 225 mm) contained >60% of CWD C and N stocks in our study, and are
489 known to provide essential habitat to rare and threatened fauna (Hollis 2011).

490 In addition to prescribed fire *per se*, the type of prescribed fire influenced CWD stocks by
491 decay and size class. Significantly less C and N stocks in rotten decay classes (D4, D5) in High
492 than Low frequency fire treatments supports the above indications that combustion losses of
493 susceptible decayed wood increased with the number of low-intensity fires. In addition, prescribed
494 fire season influenced C and N stocks in the largest CWD (>500 mm diameter), which were less in
495 Autumn than Spring fire treatments. This effect was likely associated with the drier conditions of
496 Autumn than Spring fires. That is, significantly less mean total rainfall in the 3-month pre-fire

497 periods, and significantly higher mean FFDI and SDI in Autumn than Spring fires, are strong
498 indicators of lower moisture content of eucalypt CWD (Burrows 1987). In turn, CWD
499 consumption by fires would likely increase with decreasing moisture content (Knapp et al. 2005),
500 with a significant effect on only the largest logs likely reflecting lower responsiveness with
501 increasing diameter to short-duration rain in the pre-fire period (Burrows 1987, Defo and Brunette
502 2006).

503 *CWD stocks of pyrogenic carbon*

504 Repeated low-intensity prescribed fires increased the pyrogenic (char) C in CWD by 0.26
505 Mg ha⁻¹, representing an increase from 0.1 to 2% of total C in CWD. Comparative data are lacking
506 (Adams and Attiwill 2011), although, based on similar methods and CWD size classes, Donato *et*
507 *al.* (2009) estimated CWD pyrogenic C production of 0.27 Mg ha⁻¹ after a single stand-replacing
508 wildfire, and 0.59 Mg C ha⁻¹ after two such fires in north-west USA. Elsewhere, rates of CWD C
509 conversion to pyrogenic C have fallen in the range 1 to 11% for a range of fire conditions
510 including an 'intense crown fire' (Preston and Schmidt 2006).

511 Our data indicate low potential for CWD to act as a long-term pyrogenic C stock under
512 regimes of repeated low-intensity prescribed fire. Stocks of CWD char were low, and while they
513 increased with prescribed fire frequency, such increases were one to two orders of magnitude
514 lower than overall decreases in total C stocks in Fire relative to Control treatments. Furthermore,
515 there seems little scope to markedly increase CWD pyrogenic C stocks with both current low rates
516 of CWD inputs, and a high likelihood of consumption in subsequent prescribed fires (Preston and
517 Schmidt 2006). However, this does not discount the importance of CWD as a source of pyrogenic
518 C to soils, where its residence time can be in the order of 100s to 1000s of year (Lehmann et al.

519 2008). As such, the effects of repeated low-intensity prescribed fires on the quantities and
520 composition of char in soils is the focus of our ongoing research.

521 *Conclusions*

522 Our study demonstrates that repeated low-intensity prescribed fires have the potential to
523 significantly decrease CWD stocks (biomass, C, N), in pieces of all sizes and particularly decayed
524 pieces, and to change CWD chemical attributes (C and N concentrations, C to N ratios). In
525 addition, our data indicate CWD would at best be a minor and transient stock of pyrogenic C under
526 regimes of repeated prescribed fires. From a management perspective, these findings point to a
527 potential trade-off between sustained reduction of wildfire risk, and the consequences of decreased
528 CWD C stocks, and of changes in the form of CWD as a substrate for habitat and in
529 biogeochemical processes. An optimum prescribed fire regime would aim to effectively decrease
530 finer CWD fuels (S1), which influence fire behavior, while maintaining stocks of large and
531 decayed CWD, which have multi-faceted roles in forest biodiversity and functioning. Our study
532 indicates that, for temperate eucalypt forests, fire intervals near 10 rather than 3 years would offer
533 the best scope for decreasing losses of decayed CWD, while fires under moist spring rather than
534 dry autumn conditions would better conserve the largest CWD. Our data provide a strong basis for
535 evaluating the costs of management regimes that involve repeated low-intensity fires, but further
536 research is required to quantify the comparative costs of wildfire, particularly as they are mitigated
537 or not by the use of prescribed fire.

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782

Table 1. Characteristics of the prescribed fire treatments: autumn Low frequency (AL), autumn High frequency (AH), spring Low frequency (SL) and spring High frequency (SH). Significant effects of fire season (S), fire frequency (Fq) and their interaction (SxFq) on fire attributes are indicated (* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; *ns*, no significant effects detected).

	Treatment				Effects
	AL	AH	SL	SH	
Mean burn interval (yr) *	11.9 ± 1.6	4.0 ± 0.4	8.8 ± 0.1	3.1 ± 0.2	S*; Fq***
Number of prescribed fires *	2.6 ± 0.2	5.4 ± 0.4	3.0 ± 0.0	6.8 ± 0.2	S**; Fq***
Years since last prescribed fire *	6.0 ± 0.8	4.4 ± 0.4	7.0 ± 0.0	4.0 ± 0.0	Fq***
Flame height (m) †‡	0.45 ± 0.07 [10]	0.34 ± 0.04 [20]	0.41 ± 0.05 [15]	0.43 ± 0.06 [33]	ns
Fire rate of spread (m min ⁻¹) †‡	0.38 ± 0.05 [8]	0.65 ± 0.13 [13]	0.98 ± 0.18 [10]	1.52 ± 0.37 [24]	S*
Scorch height (m) †‡	7.5 ± 1.3 [9]	5.7 ± 1.0 [15]	6.8 ± 1.6 [15]	4.4 ± 0.6 [29]	Fq*
Forest Fire Danger Index	7 ± 2 [12]	6 ± 1 [27]	3 ± 0 [15]	4 ± 1 [34]	S***
Soil Dryness Index †¶	125 ± 12 [12]	111 ± 7 [27]	19 ± 2 [15]	30 ± 2 [34]	S***, SxFq*
3 months rainfall pre-fire (mm) †¶	109 ± 14 [10]	109 ± 9 [22]	210 ± 24 [9]	227 ± 9 [27]	S***

* Values are mean ± SE across the five study areas (since the experiment was established in 1985)

† Values are mean \pm SE [number of fires observed for that attribute]

‡ Mean flame height, fire rate of spread and scorch height were visually estimated during the burns (Tolhurst and Flinn 1992)

[¶] Mean Forest Fire Danger Index (Luke and McArthur 1978), mean Soil Dryness Index (Mount 1972) and mean total rainfall in the 3 months before fires were based on rainfall recorded at automated weather stations within 4 km of each study area, and on air temperature and relative humidity measured within each study area before fires using a Bacharach sling psychrometer (Tolhurst and Flinn 1992).

FIGURE LEGENDS

FIG. 1. Variation of C and N concentrations and of wood densities among wood types of Deeply charred (char depth > 0.5mm) and Non-charred coarse woody debris. ‘Combined’ wood relates to Small coarse woody debris pieces (≤ 225 mm diameter) of a single wood type; other wood types were present in Small pieces of decay classes 4 and 5, and Large pieces of all decay classes. Values are mean (\pm SE) of 13 to 45 values per wood type/char combination. Letters indicate significant differences among wood types for each variable ($P < 0.05$; Tukey’s HSD test), and asterisks indicate significant differences between char classes within wood types (** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; t-test).

FIG. 2. C and N concentrations, C to N ratio, and wood density of whole CWD pieces by decay class and char class (Non-charred, Deeply charred to depth > 0.5mm). Values are the mean (\pm SE) of 13 to 20 pieces per decay/char combination (but 2 pieces for D1/Deeply charred combination), and were based on wood types aggregated by piece (using the proportional contribution of each wood type to the piece’s full circular cross-sectional area). Letters indicate significant differences among decay classes ($P < 0.05$; Tukey’s HSD test), and asterisks indicate differences between char classes within decay class (* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$; t-test). There were no detected significant interactions between decay and char classes for any CWD attributes.

FIG. 3. Mean counts (100 m^{-1}) of CWD pieces by decay, size, and char classes. Total counts are the means (\pm SE) of $n=20$ plots per treatment. Treatment abbreviations: ‘Control’ non-burnt control; ‘A’ autumn; ‘S’ spring; ‘H’ High frequency; ‘L’ Low frequency. Total counts were significantly lower in Fire than Control treatments ($P < 0.01$; no significant overall effects of fire

season or frequency). Significant effects of prescribed fire (Control 'C' versus Fire 'F'), fire season (Autumn 'A' versus Spring 'S') and fire frequency (High 'H' versus Low 'L') by decay, size and char classes were as indicated (* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$). Decay classes: D1, no decay; D2, weakly decayed; D3, moderately decayed; D4, very decayed; D5, substantially decayed. Diameter size classes: S1: 25 – ≤75 mm; S2: 75 – ≤150 mm; S3: 150 – ≤225 mm; S4: 225 – ≤500 mm; S5: >500 mm. Char classes: Non-charred, Superficially charred (char depth ≤0.5 mm), Deeply charred (char depth >0.5 mm).

FIG. 4. CWD stocks of C (Mg ha^{-1}) and N (kg ha^{-1}) by prescribed fire treatment, and by decay and size classes. Treatment abbreviations: 'Control' non-burnt control; 'A' autumn; 'S' spring; 'H' High frequency; 'L' Low frequency. Total stocks are the means (\pm SE) of $n=20$ plots per treatment. Total C and N stocks were significantly greater in Control than Fire treatments ($P < 0.05$), with no significant differences between fire seasons or frequencies, but a significant season by frequency interaction ($P < 0.05$). Significant effects of prescribed fire (Control 'C' versus Fire 'F'), fire season (Autumn 'A' versus Spring 'S') and fire frequency (High 'H' versus Low 'L') by decay and size classes were as indicated (* $P < 0.05$; ** $P < 0.01$; *** $P < 0.001$). Decay classes: D1, no decay; D2, weakly decayed; D3, moderately decayed; D4, very decayed; D5, substantially decayed. Diameter size classes: S1: 25 – ≤75 mm; S2: 75 – ≤150 mm; S3: 150 – ≤225 mm; S4: 225 – ≤500 mm; S5: >500 mm.

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Appendix

Table A1. Number of pieces and wood type samples used to characterize CWD. Values are given for each size (Small ≤ 225 mm; Large > 225 mm) and decay class (and sum to a total of 323 wood-type samples)

	CWD pieces	Wood type			
		Combined	Hard	Soft	Crumbly
Small					
Decay 1	12	12			
Decay 2	19	19			
Decay 3	20	20			
Decay 4	20	15	5	5	5
Decay 5	16	3	13	13	12
Sub-total	87	69	18	18	17
Large					
Decay 1	6		6	6	2
Decay 2	16		16	15	4
Decay 3	20		20	20	8
Decay 4	19		19	19	15
Decay 5	17		17	17	17
Sub-total	78	0	78	77	46
Total	165	69	96	95	63